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Key Words: FMEA, FMECA, Automated FMEA, Matrix FMEA

Abstract

If FMEAs are to provide meaningful and useful results, techniques which are both standard and automated must be developed. A survey of current FMEA techniques and automation tools is presented. The feasibility and practicality of developing a standardized, automated FMEA technique is addressed. The framework for a computerized technique, based upon matrix FMEA and consistent with the guidance provided in MIL-STD-1629A, is discussed. The technique provides: a functional top-down FMEA during early development phases; a top-down and bottom-up approach when equipment/system hardware elements and their configuration have been defined; and information which can be used for maintainability, testability, and logistics studies. The paper addresses the specifics of this procedure and its application.

Introduction

Failure Modes and Effects Analysis (FMEA) is a broad area of systems analysis. The true power of the FMEA is in its use as a design tool. The FMEA can be used to support reliability, maintainability, testability, safety and logistics analyses. When performed in an accurate and timely fashion, the FMEA can be an invaluable source of information for the design of test systems, the development of trouble shooting procedures, the planning of scheduled maintenance, and the development of integrated diagnostics capabilities. In addition, an effective FMEA presents a thorough examination of a system's strengths and weaknesses.

The power of the FMEA as a design tool has been recognized increasingly by both Government and industry. But with this recognition has come the realization that in order to be used effectively, the FMEA must become a much more efficient process. The FMEA technique needs to be more effective in: 1) time and cost; 2) thoroughness and accuracy; and 3) efficient in application to a spectrum of related analysis areas, such as maintainability, testability and logistics.

This paper will first briefly discuss the current status of FMEA techniques and present the results of a survey which defines their current level of automation. Finally, the feasibility and practicality of developing a standardized, automated FMEA technique or framework appropriate for application in reliability, maintainability, testability and logistics will be addressed.

Current FMEA Techniques and FMEA Automation

A large number of techniques have been developed for use in performing FMEA. In an evolutionary sense, the development of new techniques has not fostered the elimination of earlier techniques, but has served to augment the older techniques or to provide a new approach for a specific problem area. As shown in Table 1, the techniques which have been developed for FMEA fall into four general categories: traditional FMEA,

tree techniques, combinations of techniques, and alternate techniques.

Most FMEA techniques exhibit tremendous potential for automation. Many automated clerical tools have been developed for FMEA. Clerical tools for tabular FMEA have been developed concurrently with other word processing applications. The analysis of failure modes, however, has not been automated. The actual data input and analysis is still performed by the engineer.

In this section, the results of a survey of currently available FMEA techniques and automated tools will be presented. For each of the four categories in Table 1, a short description of each technique will be presented (which will provide an indication of its potential for automation) and the currently available automated tools for their analysis will be discussed.

Traditional FMEA Techniques - What They Are

The traditional FMEA techniques originated with the development of the tabular "worksheet" FMEA. The FMEA worksheet provides a simple inductive approach which is viable at any stage in design. The worksheet can be tailored to the needs of the analyst, providing specific information in areas such as failure predictability and fault isolation.

Matrix FMEA was developed (Ref 1) as an attempt to create an easily traceable and understandable analysis. The format used for Matrix FMEA is a gridded plot of failure effects vs. inputs, outputs, connections, and parts. The lower levels of analysis feed directly into the next higher level matrix in a "build-up" process.

Traditional FMEA techniques have also been developed for software and microprocessor systems. Software FMEA (Ref 2) is designed to provide a functional analysis of the software limitations in meeting specific design requirements. Microcomputer FMEA (Ref 3) is used to analyze completely designed systems in a real-time operating situation. Currently no traditional FMEA technique is available which can be used for all design stages in software and integrated hardware/software developments.

The failure combination method and hardware/software interface analysis require a previously completed tabular FMEA. The failure combination method (Ref 4) explores the effects of multiple failures and externally induced failures. Various combinations of single, multiple and externally induced failures are categorized according to their effect on the system. Hardware/software interface analysis (Ref 5) examines every failure mode for potential hardware/software interface problems. A series of questions is asked of every failure mode to determine if the software can cope with the failure and provide for continued operation and use the full capability of the hardware without overstressing it.

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Current Automation of Traditional FMEA Techniques

Most clerical automated tools have been developed to support tabular FMEA techniques. A wide range of clerical aids currently exist and will not be discussed.

One of the first nonclerical automated FMEA techniques was developed in 1978 by Legg (Ref 6). FUME (FMEA Using Matrix Effects) checks a matrix FMEA for consistency and also calculates probabilities of failure. The program translates the input into matrix line statements and checks the statements for consistency. Probabilities of failure are calculated by obtaining the summation of failure rates along a horizontal matrix vector at each occurrence of the effect. The program calculates failure probability based on a user supplied operating time. The FUME program does not perform any circuit analysis and does not provide for the inclusion of tailoring information.

Tree Techniques - What They Are

The tree techniques are failure modes and effects analyses which produce an evaluation of a system in a progressive manner. The tree techniques examine the progression of failures, time, or current and logic flow in electronic systems. The tree techniques are all graphically oriented.

In fault tree analysis a specific undesirable system state or failure (top event) is defined. The fault tree is then developed using deductive reasoning and the principles of Boolean logic. Once the fault tree has been constructed it can be analyzed using Boolean algebra. Fault tree analysis is especially useful in the analysis of highly interfaced systems and fault tolerant designs.

Sneak circuit analysis is used to find design errors which could result in improper or undesirable system operations. In sneak circuit analysis the circuit or flow system is characterized as a combination of standard topological patterns (network trees). For each pattern a series of clues has been developed to aid the analyst in identifying the existence of sneak paths, sneak timing, sneak labels, and sneak indications.

System state phase modelling (Ref 7) uses a logic diagram which resembles a tree with switches along each branch to investigate all possible system states. The logic diagram includes paths for operational, degraded, and failed system states. Unlike previously discussed techniques, system state phase modelling allows the entire operational history in the system to be carried through the analysis.

Event-sequence analysis (Ref 8) traces the effects of system failures as a function of the order in which they occur. The event-sequence map is a tree-like structure; the branches of the map represent the time sequenced order of faults. The map shows all probable failure histories for system operation. Numerical evaluation can be made of the event-sequence map using conditional probabilities of event occurrences.

Software sneak analysis is very similar to sneak circuit analysis, both in intent and approach. The

analysis is capable of locating sneak outputs, sneak inhibits, sneak timing, and sneak messages, as well as other programming bugs.

Current Automation of Tree Techniques

The automation which currently exists for fault tree analysis includes programs for both the logical analysis of the constructed fault tree and the actual construction of the tree. Computer codes in the public domain which perform qualitative fault tree analysis include: PREP, ELRAFT, MOCUS, SETS, and ALLCUTS. Computer programs for quantitative analysis which exist in the public domain include: KITT, FRANTIC, WAM-BAM, WAM-CUT, PATREC, PATREC-MC, and SAMPLE. The major drawback associated with the current programs is the long computing time required for the analysis of large trees. Fault tree construction methods have grown to include computer-aided generation of fault trees based on directed graphs (computer-aided synthesis, Ref 9) and decision tables (CAT method, Ref 10). The development of the models to be used in the automatic generation of fault trees has proven to be a large undertaking. As a result, fault trees are still often generated by hand.

Computer assistance for sneak circuit analysis has been available since 1967. (Digital logic circuits, however, are not easily handled by automation and are often done by hand.) The computer processes the input circuit topography. The data is converted into nodes, paths, and nodal sets. Nodal sets are indexed and cross-referenced by the computer. The computer also produces the network tree and identifies the topological patterns in the tree.

The mathematical evaluation of event-sequence maps has been automated by Kaman Sciences, Inc. in the proprietary program GO.

Combinations of Techniques - What They Are

The FMEA techniques which represent combinations of other analysis techniques were developed to avoid specific shortcomings found in older techniques. Tabular systems reliability analysis (Ref 11) combines aspects of the tabular FMEA, fault tree analysis, and Markov chain theory. The analysis provides a high level evaluation of system performance. It is well suited for providing design evaluations of fault tolerant distributed systems. Integrated critical path analysis (Ref 12) examines hardware/software interrelationships in a system. The technique combines aspects of tabular FMEA, fault tree analysis, and sneak circuit analysis. The technique does not have the rigid structure as found in other techniques. It does, however, present a broad evaluation of both hardware and software responses to failures.

Current Automation of Combination Techniques

The numerous applications and wide range of data in the combination techniques make automation a highly desirable feature. An automated procedure, TASRA, (Ref 11) presently exists for tabular systems reliability analysis. The automated program manipulates the decision tables prepared by the analyst.

The program systematically examines all possible combinations of system states and presents them for analyst evaluation. The program is also capable of performing the mathematical analyses to determine the probabilities of specific system states. TASRA has been widely employed as an analysis technique for fault tolerant designs.

Alternate Techniques - What They Are

The LAM technique and approachability analysis do not fall neatly into any of the other three categories of techniques for FMEA. The LAM technique (Ref 13) characterizes system effectiveness in terms of the physical parameters of the system. Coupled differential equations are developed to model the behavior of the system for both normal and perturbed operation. Mathematical analysis of the equations allows the effects of hardware failures to be determined. Approachability analysis (Ref 14) is performed to evaluate the topographical design/layout of a system. Using a matrix approach, the technique investigates potential failures resulting from the improper relationship of parts, the introduction of foreign materials, and external stresses. Design and layout changes can be suggested by the results of approachability analysis.

Current Automation of Alternate Techniques

The LAM technique is highly analytical, and neither the development of the state equations nor the analytic solution of the equations is completely suitable for automation. Automated techniques for the evaluation of failures caused by approach are not currently available.

Development of a Standardized, Automated FMEA Technique

The task of developing a standardized, automated FMEA technique requires the following:

1. Assessing the feasibility and practicality of developing such a technique;
2. Defining the standard procedures and associated data requirements for the technique; and
3. Developing the computer programs to automate the technique.

This section will address the feasibility and practicality of developing a standardized, automated FMEA technique and will present a framework for the development of such a technique.

Feasibility and Practicality

As has been shown in the previous discussion, most FMEA techniques are strong candidates for automation. Each technique, however, has distinct limitations associated both with its general use and with its ability to be fully automated. The various attempts which have been made to provide an automated FMEA capability attest to the fact that a standardized, automated FMEA procedure would be desirable.

The major obstacle to developing a standardized technique is the lack of a technique which provides a

thorough, accurate, traceable analysis which also supplies the additional information required for allied analyses. The development of such a technique, based upon those techniques previously discussed, is considered feasible.

As the previous discussion has shown, automation of the clerical portions of any FMEA technique is both feasible and practical. If the automated FMEA technique is to be capable of maturing with the design and supporting allied analyses, the analysis data base should be automated. Data base automation has been shown to be both feasible and practical.

The major obstacle to the automation of any FMEA technique is the automation of the analysis/evaluation portions of the procedure. The analysis/evaluation of the effects of failure is difficult to accomplish automatically. The analysis of failure effects for preliminary design stages requires a high-level functional approach. Automation tools do not currently exist for this level of analysis. The definitions of functional failures are highly application dependent. The automation of functionally modelling systems could prove to be a complex and time consuming process. The development of techniques which are capable of accurately modelling systems in their early design stages is not considered to be practical at this time. At the piece part level, the automation of failure effects analysis would require circuit analysis programs capable of fault simulation. CAD system programming is the most promising area for providing the tools for mechanical and circuit analysis. But, because analysis programs are highly specialized (e.g., digital only), uniquely formatted, require large amounts of memory, and often are proprietary, the automation of the actual analysis of failure effects is not considered to be feasible at this time.

In addressing the feasibility and practicality of developing a standardized, automated FMEA technique, MIL-STD-1629A, "Procedures for Performing a Failure Modes, Effects and Criticality Analysis," was reviewed. The material contained in MIL-STD-1629A does not limit the feasibility or practicality of developing a standardized, automated FMEA technique. In fact, MIL-STD-1629A does not provide guidance for the technical approach to be taken in performing the analysis nor does it provide any exemplary material. The standard does, however, provide specific requirements for data and documentation of the analyses.

A Framework for Standardization and Automation

In an effort to provide a complete FMEA capability, Rome Air Development Center has contracted with Hughes Aircraft Company⁽¹⁾ to develop a standardized, automated FMEA technique for electronic systems. The technique will provide a procedure which is standardized in terms of program phasing, analysis depth, failure modes investigated, analysis content, and analysis presentation. The automated portions of the technique will include all clerical

(1) Contract F30602-82-C-0072

functions (generation of MIL-STD-1629A forms, graphical outputs, etc.), calculation of failure mode criticality and BIT detectability (based on user supplied data), and transfer and manipulation of design and failure mode data contained in the data base.

The standardized FMEA technique will provide analysis procedures for all phases of the design cycle, from concept to production. The integrated approach employed in the development of the standardized FMEA technique allows both the analysis itself and its supporting data base to mature as the design matures. The inputs and outputs of each procedure will be compatible with the inputs and outputs of the other procedures. The compatibility of inputs and outputs will allow easy transition and update of design data.

During the conceptual and early design stages, a functional analysis using a top-down approach will be used. The development of the functional analysis procedure will be tailored for use with conceptual requirements statements and block diagrams. Mission critical functions can be identified and subjected to design controls at this early stage in design.

The original analysis can be updated as the design progresses in the demonstration and validation phase. During this phase a top-down/bottom-up analysis procedure will be developed. The bottom-up analysis procedure will be used to validate the top-down analysis which has been developed as the design has matured. The detailed analysis procedure will include provisions for standard inputs, characteristic failure modes, and typical output considerations. The procedure will be based upon a modified matrix format which includes commentary material. The growth of the analysis will help to identify critical components at an early stage and will help to better define the level of critical failures which should be considered in accordance with MIL-STD-1629A. The approach employed in this procedure will help to eliminate the analysis "overkill" characteristic of piece part FMEAs.

Once the design configuration has been set, the standardized FMEA procedure will provide for update of design information as the system is tested and deployed. The update procedure will allow for the inclusion of unexpected failure modes, test results, and failure analysis results.

The standardized procedure will be capable of analyzing electronic designs and will contain provisions for the limited treatment of complex microcircuitry. No provision has been made for the treatment of software. The information developed during the FMEA will be sufficient to allow for criticality analysis, the determination of Built-in-Test and test point adequacy, and support of maintainability, testability and logistics analyses.

The standardized technique will be automated to the extent found to be practical. The clerical functions, basic calculations and data base manipulations will be completely automated. The analyst, however, will be required to perform the actual analysis of failure effects and will be required to supply failure rate information and failure severity estimations.

The automated technique will provide for both the traditional tabular representation of the analysis in MIL-STD-1629A formats and the matrix FMEA representation. The automated procedure will be based, in part, on the existing matrix program FUME. The data base will be developed to support the matrix FMEA approach. This approach insures the traceability of the analysis and allows for data base manipulations to provide information for allied analyses in safety, testability and maintainability. Additional commentary material will also be included in the data base along with the system matrices. The matrix format was chosen as the basis for the automated procedure because of its graphic format and its potential for multi-discipline application.

The standardized, automated FMEA technique will be user friendly and will be provided with a users manual containing exemplary information. The technique will be capable of providing the following analyses based upon user supplied information:

- . Mission Phases Summary
- . Matrix FMEA Output
- . Tabular FMEA Output
- . Failure Mode Dictionary
- . Failure Effect Dictionary
- . Systems Indications Summary
- . Systems Control Summary
- . Criticality Analysis
- . BIT Detectability Analysis

Hughes has estimated that clerical labor savings of at least fifty percent could be realized with the use of the standardized, automated technique. Further, the direct labor savings involved in extracting information for allied analyses could be as great as eighty percent. A major factor which will effect savings is the degree of industry acceptance of the technique. Effort has been made to insure the development of a technique which is easy to learn and use and which provides a wide range of application.

The standardized, automated FMEA technique is to have been delivered in December of 1983. The technique will be applicable to electronic equipment, including both analog and digital circuitry. The automated portions of the technique will be written in Fortran IV and will reside in the MULTICS system at the Rome Air Development Center, running on a Honeywell DPS 870. It is planned to integrate this technique with the ORACLE Reliability Prediction Program early in 1984. The combined programs would then be available as Government Furnished Property.

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Biography

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Heather Dussault is an electronics engineer at the Rome Air Development Center. She graduated from Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute with a B.S. in 1980 and a M.E. in 1981. Her current responsibilities include failure modes and effects analysis techniques, reliability and testability design considerations of fault tolerant systems, and the development of tools for Integrated Diagnostics. She is a member of IEEE and Tau Beta Pi.

<u>TABLE 1 - THE EVOLUTION OF FMEA TECHNIQUES</u>	
<p style="text-align: center;"><u>TRADITIONAL FMEA</u></p> <p>Tabular FMEA (1950s)</p> <p>Matrix FMEA (1977)</p> <p>Software FMEA (1979)</p> <p>Microcomputer FMEA (1982)</p>	<p style="text-align: center;"><u>SUPPLEMENTAL TO FMEA</u></p> <p>Criticality Analysis (1950s)</p> <p>Hazard Analysis (1950s)</p> <p>Failure Combination Method (1981)</p> <p>Hardware/Software Interface Analysis (1981)</p>
<p style="text-align: center;"><u>TREE TECHNIQUES</u></p> <p>Fault Tree Analysis (1965)</p> <p>System State Phase Modelling (1969)</p> <p>Event-Sequence Analysis (1975)</p> <p>Software Sneak Analysis (1975)</p>	<p style="text-align: center;"><u>ALTERNATE TREE TECHNIQUES</u></p> <p>Sneak Circuit Analysis (1967)</p>
<u>COMBINATIONS OF TECHNIQUES</u>	
<p>Tabular System Reliability Analysis (1980)</p>	<p>Integrated Critical Path Analysis (1971)</p>
<u>ALTERNATE TECHNIQUES</u>	
<p>LAM Technique (1981)</p>	<p>Approachability Analysis (1980)</p>